

EXAMINING FINANCIAL GOVERNANCE IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SAFE MOTHERHOOD INITIATIVES IN NIGERIA

Eze Oluchukwu Daniel

Department of Health Policy and Management, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20154472>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study assessed the effect of Financial Accountability on the Maternal and Child Healthcare Goals attainment in the Abiye Safe Motherhood Health Programme (ASMP), Ondo State. The study was guided by the following objectives: to determine the effect of approval procedure, the effect of accounting record keeping and the existence of segregation of duty on the attainment of maternal and child healthcare goals of ASMP in Ondo State. The study adopted survey research design and applied primary data through the administration of structured questionnaire. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and the independent t-test were used to know the relationship among the variables and to test the hypotheses of the study. All analyses were carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20. The outcome of the study showed that adequate approval procedures on programmes and adequate record keeping have significant effects on the attainment of goals of the ASMP in Ondo State. However, there was no significant relationship between segregation of duty and attainment of goals of the ASMP. The study concluded that attainment of maternal and child healthcare goals of the ASMP in Ondo State is positive and sustainable at the instance of adequate approval procedure and adequate record keeping on programmes in the State but of no significant effect when segregation of duty is considered. The implication of the study is that goals of programmes in the public sector are achievable when serious considerations are given to financial accountability and proper record keeping but with proper segregation of duty on all programmes.</p>	<p>Financial Accountability, Health Programme, healthcare, Maternal</p>

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The three tiers of Government worldwide are fundamentally saddled with the fundamental functions of providing essential basic infrastructures and services to benefit citizens (Achua, 2009). The public sector in Nigeria is established with its multifaceted programmes at every tier of government to bring developments and good

governance to every locality through programmes initiations. It is also at ensuring that developmental programmes are adequately implemented and spread to nooks and crannies of the society for the benefit of the entire citizens. Government institutions are primarily overlaid with the activities of providing beneficial services of good roads and potable water supply to citizens (Mojekwu and Ibekwe, 2012). Other programmes and services include the provisions of basic health care, education, and security of lives and properties. It aims at accomplishing these goals through the instrumentation of the provision of a clear process with resounding structures that facilitate effective managements of crucial issues in relation to making strategic decisions, management functions and control, supervision and accountability.

However, Healthcare programme as an indiscriminate programme, is a generalized utility that is expected to spread across all and sundry, races and tribes.

The government and other non-governmental organizations primarily do provide for it. Contrary to the notions of some people, everyone has one health challenge or the other whatever his race, gender, status or qualification. No one, especially women and children, is free from one health challenge or the other in life that will not necessitate the attention of healthcare system. There are indescribable health hardships being faced by citizens due to high cost of treatments and poor standard of living. This might result from excruciatingly difficult situations to have full access to sound healthcare services either in full or part to save them from dilapidating health programmes in their countries.

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) came into existence to tackle the deplorable conditions at which public services and infrastructures are in sub-Saharan countries. It therefore became expedient for every nation to key into the goals to reduce or put a stop to the scourge that these deplorable states have placed citizens in accessing better living through the provision of public services. This was aimed at reducing the lacuna that exists between the wealthy and poverty-stricken masses by providing basic social amenities and services and ensuring easy means of accessing them (Mojekwu and Ibekwe, 2012).

These goals include the consideration for promoting gender equality, empowering women empowerment as appropriate, eradication of poverty and hunger rates among people; ensuring universal primary education to all and sundry; reducing as much as possible maternal and child mortality rates; combating HIV/AIDS, improving maternal health, malaria and other diseases; ensuring environmental sustainability and developing a global partnership for development (World Bank, 2004).

Many children risk dying because they lack maternal care due to the death of their mothers while many unnecessary deaths of pregnant women were recorded during childbirth. It is nauseating and on record that the Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) in Nigeria is on the high side despite the attention given to it (WHO, 2012). Hence, it indicates a high index for the maternal mortality rate (MMR) in the country when compare with ratios from developed worlds. The world health community in its millennium declaration was motivated, due to the high MMR, to include the maternal and child healthcare programmes among its developmental goals to be benefited by pregnant women and children under ages 5 (World Bank, 2004).

Statement of the Problem

The Abiye safe and motherhood programme ASMP was floated to take care of the surge in health challenges encountered by pregnant women and children between ages 0 and 5 in Ondo State. To achieve this, the Ondo State government devoted large chunk of its budget to the health sector especially for the ASMP and made every necessary human, material and legal resources available for the purpose. However, some brewing issues are not without notice which call for the attention of the researcher despite the necessary attention given to ensure the

success of the programme in the State. Problems of accountability coupled with traditional accustomed way of delivery, which involve service diversion, inappropriate or poor accounting record keeping, single personnel handling transactions from its beginning to the end, not following appropriate approval procedures on transactions and lack of due process in handling transactions are noticed in the system (Olurankinse, 2012).

There are some intrinsic threats that the researcher is suspecting inherent in the ASMP which may cause its goals to be hampered especially considering sales made without proper receipting, monies received on sales not timely remitted to appropriate channels, facilities that are meant to be free are sold to patients. The researcher also assumes that some of the documents of the programme are shoddily kept, approval procedures are breached, authorization of transactions and verifications of financial documents are done by the same set of employee against the tenet of accountability and financial regulations that guide the financial operations of the organization are not followed. All these are general recklessness in managing public funds if any of them is found in the operations of the Maternal and Child Healthcare system in Ondo State, which will be tantamount to failed purposes.

Unfortunately, there has been no frantic effort to assess the effect that approval procedures, accounting record keeping and internal control system for receipts and payments transactions and segregation of duty have on the attainment of the goals of ASMP in Ondo State. It is in the light of above observations that the researcher wishes to evaluate the effect of financial accountability on the attainment of the maternal and child healthcare goals of ASMP in Ondo State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

The menace of losing life when giving it prompted the World Health Organization to come up with the MDGs 4 and 5 to reduce maternal mortality and child mortality rates in developing countries Nigeria inclusive. Maternal death relates to the death of a woman at pregnancy measured at one death per every 100,000 live deliveries while the child death involves death of a child before his/her one-year birthday. It is measured at one death per every 1,000 infants. Ogunjimi et al (2012) lament the spate at which pregnant women and children die because of either prenatal complication or postnatal complication. Statistics have it that over 14% of world maternal mortality comes from Nigeria. Hence, the urgent need for the adoption of MDGs to alleviate this menace. NSHDP (2010) estimated that for every child delivery on hourly basis in Nigeria four (4) maternal deaths do occur. This customarily may affect the continued existence of those babies in the long run.

Associated with the high maternal and child mortality rates in Nigeria is poor socio-economic development, weak health care system, lack of skill attendants, poor infrastructures, poor medical facilities, low health related literacy rate and acute shortage of medical professionals (Olusegun, 2012). Statistics have it that the ratio of medical doctors to patients in Nigeria is estimated at 1:700. Udofia and Okonofua (2008) explain the deplorable state of maternal and child health in Nigeria as hectic. Many other factors contribute to the ill-fated situations that many pregnant women and children are. Some of them lack nutritional foods, lack of appropriate hygiene to cater for them and the unborn babies, bad feeding habits, unavailability of food etc. Some of them do not have access to good hospitals while many are illiterates among them. Hence, many maternal deaths arise due to ignorance of the needed information that can be of help to them (Saraki, 2008).

The Abiye Safe Motherhood health programme came into being in year 2009 to foster a resounding health care delivery to pregnant women and children between ages 0 and 5 in Ondo State. The programme focused on the reduction of high maternal mortality rate, child mortality rate, ensure widespread of free health programme among

pregnant women and children (between ages 0 and 5) and to reduce the cost of treatment per pregnant mother and child in Ondo State. The term “Abiye” is a household name among the Yoruba, which means “Safe Delivery” of babies by pregnant women. The programme was aimed at battling the high mortality rates that was prevalent among pregnant women and children in Ondo State. It focuses on tackling complications that may arise in pregnant women, inability to access health-related facilities by pregnant women and children, bad referral system that exists in the health sector and delay in accessing prompt healthcare services when they arrive at the centre (Ogundipe, 2013).

Empirical Reviews

The issue of Public Sector Accounting has not received enough academic attention until recently when researchers started delving into it. Nothing was virtually done by researchers on Government Accounting until 1992 despite government backing given to the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, (ICAN) by an Act of Parliament in 1965 (Omolehinwa and Naiyeju, 2012). As a result, few empirical evidences could be gathered on this germane study.

Oladapo, Lamina and Fakoya (2006) carried out a study focusing the magnitude and distribution of maternal death in Sagamu, Ogun State on 2,728 deliveries between 2000 and 2005. Using retrospective descriptive analysis on the data gathered they found that maternal mortality ratio of 2989.2 per 100,000 live births was significantly higher when compared with the corresponding reported data of the same area between 1988 and 1997. Hence, many pregnant women in the area lost their lives from preventable causes of maternal death from hypertensive disorder, abortion, eclampsia, poor funding of the health sector by the government, misuse of available financial and non-financial resources by administrators of the programme and low education among women. Misuse of resources available for programmes deprive the beneficiaries from getting all the benefits that accrue to the programme and the programme will not be able to achieve its aims. The study concluded that maternal and child mortality ratio increased than before apparently due to improper handling of available resources, improper antenatal care, poor referral system and poor service delivery. The little available fund if well channeled into the programme will have a long way to go in reducing the MMR.

Employing descriptive statistics and logistic regression analysis on the relevant secondary data gathered by the researcher to examine the differential factors that affect utilization of maternal health services to reduce incidence of maternal and child mortality rate in Nigeria considering the six geopolitical zones of the country, Adamu (2011) considered the utilization of maternal healthcare services. He found that women in the Southern Region of the country utilize maternal healthcare services more than women from other regions. This was predominantly premised on health awareness among women in the region, family wealth index, closeness to facility and its availability. Consequently, availability of services to improve the health of children and pregnant women and to achieve the MDGs on maternal and child health involve adequate funding of the programme, widespread awareness among women and being accountable for every kobo that is injected into the programme by its administrators.

The study conducted by Onuorah and Appah (2012) examine empirically the level of accountability by public office holders in the Nigeria public sector considering the data obtained on total expenditure and revenue between 1961 and 2008 from the Statistical Bulletin of CBN. The researchers examine the management of public fund by office holders and the level of their responsiveness to rendering of their stewardship at the appropriate time. Using Ordinary Least Square (Multiple Regression) they found that the level of accountability is very poor in the Nigeria

public sector because the attributes of accessibility, comprehensiveness, relevance, quality, reliability and timely disclosure of economic, social and political information about government activities are completely non-available or partially available for citizens to assess and to determine the performances of public officers mostly the political office holders. The paper recommended that for accountability to thrive in the Nigeria public sector and to manage public funds efficiently level of corruption must be reduced, public sector accounting and auditing standards must be raised among administrators. Consequently, level of accountability by public office holders and the genuineness of information that they release on the resources and wealth of the public in their care is relatively low. Lack of appropriate and up-to-date information may invariably hinder citizens from holding accountable the administrators of such programme. Hence, the need for better and improved financial accountability among operators in the public sector to be able to attain the goals of programmes.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical frameworks underpinning this study are rooted in the Compliance model of Accountability.

Compliance Model of Accountability:

Wolf and Hassel (2001) in their seminal work titled the Effectiveness and Accountability: the Compliance Model provides a platform upon which accountability in the public sector is anchored if the attainment of goals of programmes is in focus. It focuses on the effectiveness of outcomes or results that are expected from a public oriented programme and stipulate the rules of behavior of the principal and agent in a clear form from the inception of the programme with the need for strict compliance to those rules through proper monitoring of the agents. It is a model that explores the accountability procedures of government's involvements in special education in the USA (Wolf and Hassel, 2001). The fundamental principles/assumptions of the model involve the issuance of regulations and documentation of compliance with those regulations; public funds are accurately channeled and not misused; provision of every needed updated record of what is being achieved on the set public sector programme and maintaining of such; and proper monitoring of the activities of agents. This advances the agency theory that put all the activities of the organization into the hands of agents whose interests are often times paramount to them (Ouchi, 1980). The compliance model calls for accountability checks that look generally at the flow of documentation of the activities of the organization vis-à-vis the rules and procedures set by the principal of the programme. Where compliance to rules and regulation is not followed, warning or other strong deterrent measures may be issued to the agent. The model focuses essentially on whether or not procedural regulations are satisfied, proper steps are taken and if right paper works are processed correctly or not. This model is applicable to this study simply because it looks in-depth to procedures that are required to ensure keeping of appropriate records and compliance to regulations that are needed to ensure accountability in the public sector programmes and to achieve the goals that are expected by citizens.

Many authors and researchers have researched on the impacts of well-placed infrastructures on the wellbeing of citizens and its effects on economic and infrastructural growth of a nation (Abosedra, et al, 2009). However, many are times that citizens lament their inability to access these provisions despite the claims of every tier of government to have achieved their goals of meeting the socio-economic needs of the people. Olowookere (2005) laments that the major bane to attainment of goals of set programmes in Nigeria is lack of accountability, unreliable accounting system, incomplete data to aid proper financial management, inadequate legal framework for accounting and auditing, weak or ineffective internal control system etc. Adegite (2010) is of the view that ineffective administration is the precursor of these threats to attainment of goals in Nigeria.

Okpala (2012) in his own view observed that when proper channelization of services to appropriate quarters is in effect and people that are saddled with some tasks are accountable to their principals then the banes to development as highlighted by some authors would subside. Ayo (2004) was also of the opinion that accountability will restrain public office holders from doing the wrong thing. He reiterated that accountability involves the preparation of budget for incomes and expenditures of the organization, ensuring that procurement procedures are followed and every other transactional documentation are properly maintained in relation to the programmes in question. Researchers did not explain the extent to which accountability affects attainment of goals of programmes.

The findings from previous researches focused mainly on health programmes generally neglecting the Maternal and Child Healthcare programme. Oladapo et al (2006) examined the magnitude and distribution of maternal death in Ogun State without considering the causal agents for the magnitude and distribution. They compared the MMR of 1988 to 1997 with that of 2000 to 2005 and found out that many pregnant women lost their lives between 2005 than the previous period. They, however, studied it from the perspective of poor funding, misuse of financial and non-financial resources and low education among women in the area.

Methodology

This research work employed the survey research design involving primary data collected through the administration of structured questionnaires. The population of the study was 265 staff members, included were all medical doctors and accountants of the Mother and Child Hospital in the eight major centres where they are located in the three geopolitical zones of the State. Every member of the population was considered along as part of the sample size for the study. The data gathered were run using the Statistical Package for Social Science version 20 (SPSS 20) and analyzed using the descriptive, correlation and regression analysis. We used regression analysis to test the relationship that exists between the dependent and independent variables. Our key independent variables are the decomposed variables from financial accountability where (AP) is the Approval Procedure that should be followed as stipulated in the financial regulation of the public sector that is saddled with the programme. The Accounting Record Keeping (AR) and Segregation of Duty (SD) are part of the variables used to proxy financial accountability. However, the dependent variables involved the attainment of goals of Maternal and Child healthcare programme in Ondo State, the decision rule that was employed was to reject the null hypothesis with 95% confidence if the P-value of the independent t-test is less than the critical value (i.e. 0.05%) and to accept the null hypothesis with 95% confidence if the P-value of the t-test is greater than the critical value.

Analytical Method

The economic model that showed the relationship that exists between Goal Attainment as a function of Approval Procedure (AP), Accounting Record Keeping (AR) and Segregation of Duty (SD) was given as follows:

GA= f (AP, AR, SD) equation.....1

Multivariate Regression Model was applied to determine the effect of financial accountability on the attainment of goals of maternal and child health care programme as shown below:

GA= α + β1AP + β2AR + β3SD+ Ε equation.....2

Where α, β1, β2 and β3, are parameters for estimation in the model whereas Ε is the residual value.

The Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationships that exist among the variables and the independent t-test was employed to test the hypotheses of the study.

r = NΣxy - (Σx) (Σy) / equation.....3

√{NΣx² - (Σx)²} {NΣy² - (Σy)²} Where:

N = Number of pairs of scores x = Financial Accountability y = Goal Attainments $\sum xy$ = Sum of products of paired scores

$\sum x$ = Sum of x scores

$\sum y$ = Sum of y scores

$\sum x^2$ = Sum of squared x scores

$\sum y^2$ = Sum of squared y scores

The independent t-test was used to test whether two sets of n_1 = Total no of value in 1 set data differ significantly.

n_2 = Total no of value in 2nd set

$$t = \frac{x_1 - x_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2 + s_2^2}{n_1 + n_2}}}$$

RESULTS/FINDINGS

The bellow Table shows that two hundred and sixty five (265) copies of research questionnaires were distributed Where among members of the population. Two hundred and \bar{x}_1 = Mean of first set of value twenty-five (225) Copies were returned representing a –commendable 84.91% while the respondents representing x_2 = Mean of second set of values 15.09% withheld the remaining forty (40) copies. s_1 = Standard deviation of set of values s_2 = Standard deviation of 2nd set values

Table: Analysis of Distributed Questionnaire in Percentages

Categories	Total Distributed	Total Returned	Total Withheld	Percentage Returned
Medical Doctors	194	171	23	88.14%
Accountants	71	54	17	76.06%
Total	265	225	40	84.91%

Source: Survey Data, 2016

Test of Hypotheses

To determine the pattern and extent of relationship among the variables, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient statistics was used to inter-correlate the values of the variables, irrespective of their group. The results are presented below:

Table 2: Correlation Matrix Showing the Relationship among Variables of Study

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Sex	Marital Status	Age	Academic Status	Year of Experience	Approval Procedure	Accounting Record Segregation	Goal Attainment
Sex	225	1.40	0.92	1							
Marital Status	225	1.53	0.52	-0.12	1						
Age	225	2.64	1.09	-.155*	.661**	1					
Academic Status	225	3.37	0.57	-.047	.078	.186**	1				

Year of Experience	225	2.23	0.63	-.044	.042	.029	.095	1				
Approval Procedure	225	12.92	3.05	.060	-.063	-.090	-.014	.096	1			
Accounting Record	225	14.33	3.15	0.03	.070	.044	-.071	-.023	.366 **	1		
Segregation of Duty	225	12.81	2.63	.060	-.062	-.043	-.022	.064	.400 **	.334**	1	
Goal Attainment	225	14.60	2.39	.090	.069	.099	-.090	-.138 *	.211*	.158*	.119	1

*P<.05, **P<.01

Source: SPSS Version 20 (2018)

Table 2 presents the means score, the standard deviation and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for the variables investigated in the research. All the demographic variables- sex, marital status, age and academic status except year of experience were not significantly correlated with the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State (r = .09: P> .05), (r = .07: P> .05), (r = .10: P> .05) and (r = -.09: P< .05) respectively. The year of experience was negatively related to goals’ attainment (r = -.14: P< .05). Impliedly, as employees gain more experience on the job the lesser the rate of attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State.

On investigating the sex of respondent on goal’s attainment, it was discovered that gender did not have any significant correlation on goal attainment in public sector programmes. Every operator either male or female that is saddled with public sector responsibility is expected to work towards the goal of the organization and do every possible to be accountable to his principal.

Marital status on the other hand did not have significant effect on the attainment of goals of programme. Impliedly, goal’s attainment of programme in the public sector can be achieved irrespective of the marital status of the operator so far the agent follows the modus operandi and tenet of the programme.

The above correlation matrix in Table 2 showed that there was no significant correlation between age and attainment of goals of programme (r = .10: P> .05). Impliedly, irrespective of the age of the administrators of public sector programmes there should be the willingness to ensure that the attainment of the goals of such programme is paramount to them.

The academic statuses of respondents were equally correlated with the attainment of goals of public sector programmes. From the correlation matrix, it was discovered that every respondent knows the need for accountability despite his or her academic status.

Academic status does not determine the level of accountability and achieving of goals of programmes by its operators.

However, year of experience was negatively significant to attainment of goals of programme. A negative correlation implies that when the value of one variable increases the value of the other corresponding variable decreases. Responses from the respondents showed that staff members and administrators with lower years in service put in tangible efforts to ensure attainment of goals of programmes than those that have been on the job for longer time.

As per the main variables of the research, the approval procedures and accounting record keeping were significantly and positively related to the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State ($r = .21$; $P < .05$) and ($r = .16$; $P < .05$) respectively while the segregation of duty was not significant ($r = .12$; $P > .05$).

Hypothesis One

Summary of Independent t-test showing the Effect of Approval Procedure on the Attainment of Goals of Programmes in Ondo State

Hypothesis one that states that approval procedure has no significant effect on the attainment of programmes in Ondo State was rejected. The hypothesis so stated was intended to assess the effect that approval procedure has on the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State $\{t(223) = 2.64$; $P < .05\}$. With ($r = .21$; $P < .05$) i.e. positive correlation between approval procedures and attainment of goals of programme, it is discovered that there is significant positive effect of approval procedure on goal's attainment in the public sector. This means that approval procedure from the point of initiation of transactions to authorization did have significant effect on attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State. **Hypothesis Two**

Summary of Independent t-test showing the Effect of Accounting Record Keeping on the Attainment of Goals of Programmes in Ondo State

Hypothesis two, which states that accounting record keeping has no significant effect on the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State was discarded. The hypothesis was intended to measure the extent of the effect of accounting record keeping on the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State $\{t(223) = 2.53$; $P < .05\}$. There is a positive relationship between the two variables ($r = .16$; $P < .05$). As keeping of accounting records increase, there is a corresponding increase also in attainment of goals of maternal and child healthcare programme in the State.

Hypothesis Three

Summary of Independent t-test showing the Effect of Segregation of Duty on the Attainment of Goals of Programmes in Ondo State.

Hypothesis three, which states that there is no relationship between segregation of duty and the attainment of programmes in Ondo State was confirmed. The hypothesis was aimed at knowing the effect that segregation of duty has on attainment of goals of the maternal and child healthcare programmes $\{t(223) = -.01$; $P > .05\}$. This indicates that segregation of duty has no significant effect on the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State ($r = .12$; $P > .05$). There is no significant relationship between segregation of duty and the attainment of goals of maternal and child healthcare programme of ASMP in Ondo State. However, the two divides had the same mean scores ($X = 14.60$) indicating that either the adequate segregation of duty or otherwise, despite it been part of devolution of financial accountability, has little or no effect on the attainment of goals of programmes in Ondo State.

Discussion of Findings

MDGs of maternal and child health programmes are achievable when effective policies to achieve the goals are put in place. The research examined the effect of approval procedures on the attainment of goals of maternal and child healthcare programmes in Ondo State. These effects were measured using the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient statistics and the t-test. The results from the analysis showed a significant positive effect of approval procedures on the attainment of goals of health programme in Ondo State. In earlier researches conducted by scholars in accounting field many corroborated the fact that due process must be followed to ensure attainment of goals of programmes in the public sector. Achua (2009) and Omolehinwa (2012) empirically commented that

some of the projects and programmes in Nigeria attract variations. Due to this, whopping sum meant for programmes' developments were missing from the coffer of the government. Okpala (2012) maintained that causes of weak accountability on programme in Nigeria is traceable to financial weaknesses, financial indiscipline, lack of proper accounting records and wastages due to the presence of upward contract variations on programmes, poor budgeting, misappropriation etc in the public sector. Impliedly, weak accountability stemming from financial indiscipline on the part of administrators in the Nigerian public sector impedes economic and infrastructural development of society. They maintained that due process and adequate approval procedures are lacking in the award of contracts and execution of programmes in Nigeria.

Conclusion/Recommendation

The results from the analysis showed that attainments of the goals of government's programmes are inevitable when there is adequate budgetary provision, removal of bureaucratic bottleneck on approval procedure, and viable internal control system that can debar corruption and ensure proper accounting records keeping in the system. This finding corroborates the assertion of Omolehinwa (2012), Keller et al (2002) and Castrol et al (1999). In their assertions, they affirmed that authorization and approval of programmes and a well-implemented policy would lead to the attainment of the goals of such programmes.

The following recommendations are offered: to different interested categories based on the research findings:

- a. There is need to ensure that due process is followed. Without appropriate approval, the risk of noncompliance with the extant procedures and rules governing the activities of programmes may be unachievable. Adequate approval procedure in awarding contracts must be ensured.
- b. There is the need to strengthen better the consistency and performance in authorization, approval and segregation of duty to foster achievability of goals of programmes in Ondo State. When programmes are well monitored, duties among operators are distinctly segregated and sound internal control mechanism is put in place for thorough monitoring, leakages of funds would be reduced to the barest minimum.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, T., Bello, K. and Mensah, R. (2009). Electricity Consumption and Economic Growth: Evidence from West Africa. *Applied Energy*. 86(4): 429–432.
- Ibrahim, M., Lawal, S. A. and Okeke, P. (2016). Determinants of Organizational Performance in the Public Sector: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Studies*. 6(S7): 232–239.
- Okorie, J. O., Danladi, M. L. and Yakubu, S. T. (2007). Accountability and Transparency in Public Financial Management in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Policy Studies*. 2(1): 42–54.
- Olatunji, A. (2014). Challenges of Adopting IPSAS in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Policy and Social Research*. 6(2): 29–39.
- Ezeani, K. C. (2009). Reforming Government Accounting for Improved Accountability in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*. 1(1): 1–16.
- Anderson, P. (2005). *Social Accountability in the Public Sector: A Conceptual Approach*. Washington DC: World Bank Publications.

- Suleiman, I. S. (2014). Efficiency and Effectiveness in Nigeria's Petroleum Sector Management.
- Musa, H. S. (2011). Patterns of Maternal Healthcare Utilization in Nigeria: Regional Perspectives.
- Adebola, S. A. and Johnson, U. M. (2016). Enhancing Public Sector Accountability through Internal Audit Functions. ICAN Conference Proceedings. 893–905.
- Ogunleye, E. O. (2010). Accounting and National Development in Nigeria. *The Nigerian Accountant*. 43(1): 56–64.